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Research Article

**COMMON COMPLAINTS OF PRIMIGRAVIDA MOTHERS
REGARDING WELL-BEING OF THEIR INFANTS: A LOCAL
EXPERIENCE**Dr. Hemandas^{1*}, Dr. Abdul Rehman Siyal,² Dr. Ammara zaidi³¹MBBS, (FCPS) Paediatrics department Isra University²MBBS, DCH, MD Assistant professor, Paediatrics Department LUMHS³MBBS, Isra University Hyderabad, student of masters in maternal child health,
texila University Gyuaana South America**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine the frequency of various common types of concerns of primigravida mothers regarding their infant visiting pediatric OPD.**Setting and design:** This cross sectional study was conducted at pediatric OPD, Isra University Hospital Hyderabad.**Methods and material:** 379 primigravida mothers having baby <2 months of age consented to participate in the study. Infants having problem for which hospital admission was indicated were excluded. Mothers were asked and data was collected for their common concerns of infants i.e. crying, feeding, sleeping, constipation, diarrhea, vomiting and appearance of baby.**Results:** Mean age \pm SD of the infants were 25.42 ± 18.18 days with a minimum age of 3 days and maximum 60 days. 54% (n=204) infants were male and 46% (n=174) were female. 19.3% (n=73) were up to one week of age, 44.1% (n=167) infants were between the age of 1week to 1 month and 36.7% (n=139) were between 1month to 2months. The most common concern with which primigravida mothers presented was feeding concerns (65.2%), followed by appearance of infant (54.9%) and sleeping concerns (52.2%), vomiting, (48.3%) and crying (42.2%). Concerns regarding constipation and diarrhea were least common i.e. (23% & 19.8% respectively). Maximum numbers of concerns (i.e. 5) were shown by 21 (5.5%) mothers.**Conclusions:** Long spells of Crying, feeding, sleep, appearance and vomiting were common concerns.**Key words:** Infants, primigravida mothers, concerns, crying, vomiting, diarrhea**Corresponding author:****Hemandas ,**MBBS, (FCPS) Paediatrics Department,
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INTRODUCTION:

One of the most stressful times in women life is birth of baby and this stress continue for early months especially with primigravida [1]. Being mother is itself a big responsibility and about 71.3% mother shows concerns which are not limited to just giving birth to child but also with providing proper care and comfort to baby [2,3]. Primigravida mothers are more anxious and less informed for health state of infant and these mothers do not differentiate the normal and abnormal routine habits of their babies. These mothers tend to visit the physician more frequently for issues of infants' health [4,5]. Mothers mainly discharged from hospital within 48 hours of postpartum period and due to very short stay at hospital, adequate amount of information is not provided to mother regarding newborn care [6,7]. Studies shows that in contrast to multigravida mothers the primigravida mothers have more concerns and anxieties regarding their ability to care her infants and need more counseling and support [8,9]. The common areas in which mother express their concerns includes: crying 87%, feeding 78%, sleeping, constipation, diarrhea, vomiting 43%, and 50% for appearance of baby [10-12]. Christie et al shown that for providing excellent post-partum care, knowledge of the mother's personal concerns about babies should be known [13]. It has been common observation that more neonates come to clinic and emergency for different complains are not medically proven or justified? So the rational of study is to determine the magnitude of various maternal concerns so that this study could develop to provide information regarding the common concerns which ultimately decrease the cost of unnecessary visits to clinic, use of medicine and admissions. This type of study is not done previously so the results of this study will also help health providers to counsel primigravida mothers.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

It was Cross-sectional study conducted at Isra University Hospital pediatric OPD Hyderabad after the after approval of synopsis. The sample size calculation was done using the raosoft software for "Sample size calculation" by using the proportion of 43.7% for vomiting, with 95 % confidential interval and 5 % of margin of error , the sample size stands to be n=379 primigravida. Sample technique was purposive sampling technique. After informed concerned primigravida from 20-30 years of having baby <2 months of age were included in

the study. Babies having problem for which hospital admission needed patients were excluded. All the mothers were asked for their common concerns of infants i.e. crying, feeding, sleeping, constipation, diarrhea, vomiting, appearance of baby etc. This information will be collected by the researcher and proforma will be filled accordingly. The variables of the study were age and sex of Baby, crying, feeding, sleeping, constipation, diarrhea, vomiting, appearance of baby. After collection of data the analyses will be conducted by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software, Version 16. Mean and standard deviation will be calculated for quantitative variables like age of baby. Frequency and percentages will be computed for qualitative variables like sex of Baby and various other concerns like crying, feeding, sleeping, constipation, diarrhea, vomiting, and appearance of baby. Data was entered and analyzed by SPSS Version 10 on Computer descriptive Synopsis Statistics.

RESULTS:

Total 379 primigravida mothers who presented with one or more health concern regarding their infants were asked to consent for the study. All of them consented and responded to the questionnaire for data collection. Mean age \pm SD of the infants were 25.42 ± 18.18 days with a minimum age of 3 days and maximum 60 days. 19.3% (n=73) were up to one week of age, 44.1% (n=167) infants were between the age of 1week to 1 month and 36.7 (n=139) were between 1month to 2 months (**Table:1**).

54% (n=204) infants were male and 64% (n=174) were female (**Figure1**).

The most common concern with which primigravida mothers presented was feeding concerns (65.2%), followed by appearance of infant (54.9%) and sleeping concerns (52.2%), vomiting, (48.3%) and crying (42.2%). Concerns regarding constipation and diarrhea were least common i.e. (23% & 19.8% respectively) (**Figure:2**).

Detailed description of the various complaints regarding these concerns is described in (**Table:2**)

According to which single most common complaint was crying of infant more than 2 hours in 162 cases (42.2%). Primigravida mothers also have concern about following like fever (53%), Jaundice (41.42%), Cord care (13.19%) and circumcision (11.8%). (**Table 3**).

Table: 1. Age of infants in different categories n=379

	Frequency	Percent
Upto One week	73	19.3
Upto One month	167	44.1
Upto 2 months	139	36.7
Total	379	100.0

Fig: 1. Gender of Infants n=379

Fig: 2. Major concerns of Primigravida mothers regarding their children n= 397

Table 2. Detailed description of different Common concerns of Primigravida mothers regarding Their Infants.397

Concerns	Complaint	Frequency	(%)
CRY	Crying for >2 hours	160	42.2
FEED	Reluctant to feed	82	21.6
	Continue BF after empty	79	20.8
	Sleep within 10 min: of emptying Breast	85	22.4
SLEEP	Sleep disturb: every 2 hours	123	32.5
	Noisy sleep pattern	92	24.3
CONSTIPATION	Pass stool after 2 days	50	13.2
	Cry during passing of stool	39	10.3
DIARRHEA	Passing stool after every feed	75	19.8
VOMITING	vomits all after feed	57	15.0
	Feed in mouth	66	17.4
	Curd like vomiting	59	15.6
APPEARENCE	Lethargic- no active movements	79	20.8
	Not gaining weight	69	18.2
	Rashes on body and face	80	21.1

Table 3: Other Concerns of mother regarding infant n= 397

Common Concern	Frequency	Percent (%)
Fever	201	53
Jaundice	157	41.42
Cord Care	50	13.19
Circumcision	45	11.8

DISCUSSION:

Literature shows that there are medical issues in early childhood period which create concerns and anxieties of mothers about baby's health. These concerns occur mostly in first time mother and can affect the mother and baby relationship [14]. Child care ranges from feeding to hygiene, from bathing to sleep, from burping to vomiting, from constipation to diarrhea and from common cold to common and rare infections [15]. It is natural for mothers to be cautious and respond to each and every move of their newborns because primigravida mothers can not differentiate the normal and abnormal routine habits of their newborns⁴. Many studies focusing on the postpartum needs of primigravida after birth of babies have found that mothers are interested to learn many issues about their infants like breastfeeding, infant behavior, cry, vomiting, rashes, childcare, infant temperature taking, infant diarrhea, constipation, circumcision, cord care and signs of infant illness etc [16-18]. This current study was done to assess the common concerns with which the primigravida mothers presented at pediatricians OPDs. To our knowledge this was

first study in Pakistan on the subject. This study was conducted in a tertiary care setup. The study enrolled primigravida mothers and asked for most common issues which they thought their infants had. The current study focused on primigravida mothers because they experience these issues first time in their lives. Their perceptions and learning needs as compared to multigravida are quite different as it was seen in a study that the primigravida women lacked confidence in themselves as new mothers regarding their ability to care for their baby [19].

Usually the mothers are very much cautious for hygiene, nutrition, safety and other needs of their infants. The infants cry for their complaints, whether it is hunger, sleep or hygiene of diaper. In the current study it was similarly seen that the primigravida mothers were mainly concerned about the crying of their infants. Primigravida mothers thought that their babies cry continuously for more than 2 hours sometimes inspite of fulfilling their needs. It has been documented in a study that sometimes babies normally cry while sleeping which is also concern for mothers. Brazelton [20] in his study elaborated the issue and described that

usually “normal” infants cry as 1 hour and 45 minutes at age 2 weeks, a peak of 2 hours and 45 minutes at age 6 weeks, decreasing to less than 1 hour at age 12 weeks. Upon stratification of infant ages the current study also found that crying of infants initially increased till one month age then it gradually decreased. Extended crying spells were documented as ranging from 46% to 87% in some study while in current study its frequency was 42% [21].

Most of the mothers including primigravida mother who begin breastfeeding stops within the first few weeks and for continuing it for longer duration of time mother needs some help like from nurse [22]. The current study asked three types of issues in this category and found that cumulatively, feeding was the most common concerns in primigravida mothers. Vomiting or regurgitation concerns were also seen commonly in 48.3% of primigravida mothers. An earlier study was documented that in about 67% of healthy infants of 4 month age regurgitate more than once a day [23]. Sleeping issues included disturbances in sleep every 2 hours and noisy sleep. It comprised of 52.2% of all in our study participants. Sleeping issues were more common in infants or one month and below that. With increase in infant's age there was decrease in sleep concerns. Compared with the study done by Wooding AR et al [24] the frequency of night awaking was about 77%. Appearance of infant including rashes on body was another common concern shown by primigravida mothers regarding their infants. It has been documented that babies can also commonly have skin problems, like diaper rash or cradle cap which may be a reason for concern for primigravida mothers. In the current study it was seen that skin rash was presented as matter of worry by 21% of primigravida mothers. In study of U.K about 20% of neonates presented to pediatricians with concern of nappy rash [25]. Other less common concerns were diarrhea and constipation. It was documented in a discussion that constipation accounts for 3-5% of pediatric office visits [26] and a quarter of pediatric gastroenterology referrals while in current study participants it was present in 10-13% of infants. Breastfed infants mostly pass three soft stools per day but it is varying from one per day to one after each feed [27]. 19.8% of mother in our study having concern of diarrhea and we found that almost all neonates were on breast feed, passing stool after every feed but gaining appropriate weight and therefore having normal breast milk stool. 53% of mother having concern that baby is felt hot on touch or baby is having fever. We found that fever or feeling hot baby's body was due to over wrapping as primigravida suspect that baby should not get cold and flu. Other reason for fever was high environmental temperature as found in other study [28]. In a local study 65.5% neonates

presented with jaundice and out of them 40.5% were having physiological jaundice. In our study mother having concern of jaundice with same figure 41.42% and that was found as physiological Jaundice. Primigravida mother also have concern of cord care (13.19%) and circumcision (11.8). It was observe that concern of circumcision was mostly by elders coming with primigravida mother and they were asking to do circumcision early.

CONCLUSION:

Long spells of Crying, feeding, sleep, appearance and vomiting were common concerns of primigravida mothers regarding their infants. Since primigravida have little knowledge about baby care, hence the proper antepartum education should be given to these primigravida women and this education can be provided either in hospital or in OPD setup by the health nurses, doctors and paramedics. All these findings warrant the intensive need of preparing and implementing educational and informative programs which focus on first time mothers. Matter of these programs should be based on research and evidence in which the findings of the current study data are helpful.

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